

APPLICATION OF MODERN METHODS IN TEACHING ENGLISH

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ABSTRACT

One of the most crucial components of tolerance in a personality culture is language learning. Since language is a tool for communication, it can be learned nearly anywhere in the home, in the community, or in a formal setting. Additionally, theory-based instruction is given on language phenomena. Language proficiency, especially multilingualism, is extremely important in today's world of active international interactions. In our country, most pupils and foreign students learn three languages. Special names are used to identify these languages. Native language, second language, and foreign language are these. The first language that functions independently in the development of thinking is the native tongue. The second language is treated as the language of its fraternity, or neighbors, which are made up of people from various nationalities when it is spoken. In this article, opinions and feedback on the use of modern methods in teaching English are kept.

Keywords: English, methodology, modern, technology, teaching, speech, didactic education, interactive education.

There are distinct concepts in each science. The educational system, the educational method, the educational principle, the educational methods, and the methodological approach are some of the key ideas incorporated into the methodology of teaching a foreign language. When a method of teaching a foreign language is referred to as a complex of actions involving both a teacher and a student, it means that it aims to meet the practical, all-encompassing, educational, and developmental objectives of doing so. The terms "sum of educational techniques" and "direction of Education" are used to refer to different aspects of education. The second meaning can be found in works on the history of teaching methodology, whereas the first is employed in educational theory in the sense of process techniques. For instance, teaching a foreign language is referred to as a translation method, togri method, conscious-comparative approach, traditional way, intensive method, etc.

The phenomena of nature and society develop in interconnected and continuous communication. Since the sciences are the inics of objective reality, none of them exists separated from the others. The phenomenon and the subject at the same time can be a

source of research in several disciplines, for example, the social phenomenon "language" from its point of view is studied by linguistics, educational science. The term "methodology of a foreign language" evokes in the mind of a person the so-called associative "connection": first of all, the totality of methods and methodological methods aimed at teaching a language is understood or scientific knowledge about teaching methods, and finally, independent pedagogical science comes to mind. The methodology of teaching a foreign language has developed in harmony with didactics, interconnected. It is undoubtedly known to all of us that the teaching theories of all academic disciplines are based on didactics, from which they receive scientific feed. Foreign Language Teaching is also based on didactics.

Linguodidactics, general theory of didactics in education, methodology as the science of instruction Linguometodics is regarded as the science of teaching a particular language, according to the General Theory of Language Teaching. The word "method" refers to the process through which a teacher-educator and student work to acquire knowledge, credentials, skills, the development of students' worldviews, and the provision of opportunities for cognition. There are numerous ways to define this idea. The implementation of techniques in the teaching of foreign languages began in distant times, while the principles are relatively newer methodological terms. The statement of grammatical knowledge was accepted as the main goal of the teaching.

In conclusion. The student's own particular interests are the most crucial responsibility of the educational process. Knowing which technology to incorporate into the teaching process will help you get the desired results. As you can see, regardless of how flawless a certain educational technology is used, it does not produce the best conditions for identifying and developing students' qualifications. The technology of pedagogical education - together with a favorable environment for students and teachers for the design, organization and conduct of the educational process, is told a well-thought-out model of educational and pedagogical activity. Pedagogical technology involves the implementation of a completely controlled idea of the educational process.

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